

Strategic Planning Document for “Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms: A Model to Empower Education Initiatives Across the Global South”

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This report is associated with the “Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms: A Model to Empower Education Initiatives Across the Global South.” This was a 2022-2023 Foundations-level (Level I) AHRC grant in the UK-US Digital Scholarship in Cultural Institutions programme, in collaboration with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH, HND-284967-22), awarded jointly to the University of Cambridge (Dr. Stefania Merlo, PI) and University of Arkansas (Dr. Carla Klehm, PI).

Overview

The AHRC-NEH grant explored how to best empower secondary school and university educators in the Global South to explore cultural heritage through digital storytelling with spatial and nonspatial data. The project coordinated with a South African-based research group whose beta-level digital archive, *metsemegologolo*, ‘ancient towns’ in Setswana, was scaling up its front-end outreach. *Metsemegologolo*, co-directed by Cambridge, KwaZulu Natal Museum and two other South African institutions, is an open-source spatial database containing heritage and archaeological objects, historical maps, and oral histories about precolonial African urbanism. The project developed a UK-US collaboration among the *metsemegologolo* developers, digital heritage experts, and southern African educators to explore digital storytelling in the Global South (<https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/digital-storytelling/>). The primary goal evaluated how to best mobilize the *metsemegologolo* archive for digital storytelling within resource-limited educational environments in southern Africa and especially South Africa.

This document summarizes a set of deliverables associated with the project. Four digital storytelling curations about African archaeology were created using the database as project participants experimented with topics, the use of spatial data, and various platforms. The US-UK collaboration culminated in an in-person workshop, held in Cambridge September 12-14 2022, that developed specific recommendations to address the challenges of digital storytelling in low-resourced environments. A final March 2023 webinar brought together thirteen experts in the digital humanities to discuss storytelling with spatial archives, digital infrastructure in low-resourced environments, and ways in which marginalised voices and perspectives can be integrated into the digital storytelling process. The webinar had over 150+ participants (more than half located in Africa) and remains accessible on the digital storytelling link referenced above. Along with a set of curated projects and educational resources. Summaries associated with the initial assessment of the *Metsemegologolo* database and its potential for educational uses within the digital humanities, a survey of digital humanities projects that involved archives and storytelling elements about African and marginalized histories, the project workshop notes and outcome, and an overview of the webinar, are all archived, open-access, at:

Initial Assessment of the *Metsemegologolo* database and its potential for educational uses within the digital humanities

The Metsemegologolo project began in 2020 under the direction of Stefania Merlo, Justine Winjes, and Anton Coetzee, based at University of Witwatersrand, University of Pretoria, and the KwaZulu Natal Museum (Republic of South Africa, or RSA hereafter). Metsemegologolo, ‘ancient towns’ in Setswana (<https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za>), is an open-source prototype database containing archaeological data, heritage objects, historical maps, oral histories and poetry about precolonial African urbanisms. One of the primary goals of the metsemegologolo database is to raise awareness of the topic of African urbanism, especially the deep-rooted nature and unique historical trajectories associated with African cities. While urban centers elsewhere are often defined by dense populations, social stratification, monumental architecture, among other traits, African urban centers, in contrast, have traditionally been characterized by high mobility, and a lack of control or dependence on central places or agriculture. In essence, African urban centers developed differently in the form and function of other early urban centers, in ways that directly play into how power operates within those societies.

While there is merit for understanding unique pasts and upending traditional narratives, there is also practical value in studying how these places have functioned over the long term, knowing that future challenges depend on deep cultural understandings. Today, Africa has one of the fastest urban growth rates in the world: by 2050, these cities will be home to 90 million people more than presently are, with a quarter of the world’s population living in Africa more generally; by the end of this century it is estimated that the world’s biggest cities will be concentrated in Africa. Understanding long-term trajectories and historical contingencies that have influenced these places are key for effective local governmental and international policy for sustainable growth.

The metsemegologolo platform is organized through spatial relationships that are reflected both in the production of the metadata and in the embedding of geographic information (via registration of geographic coordinates) into the objects themselves. The environment includes an interface for a geographically based and interactive display and analysis of five interrelated components: (1) a searchable text-based database of materials relevant for sites and archaeological structures; (2) a photo and image archive; (3) an object archive; (4) a linguistic archive; (5) various Geographic Information System (GIS) layers integrating a range of historical and contemporary information. All materials will be geolocated and keyed to search terms in the database. The platform uses a flexible, extensible data framework designed around the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model, which is intended to provide for metadata and information interchange within the digital heritage realm. The customized archive is currently being populated in two modes: upload of single digital objects and creation of the metadata directly in the archival platform (this process was used for complex spatial objects such as point and line shapefiles of archaeological landscape features and 3D large objects) and bulk upload of text, image and 3D files from a Google sheet containing digital objects and their metadata

In our initial virtual meetings, the metsemegologolo project members identified challenges related to: 1) digital storytelling in low-resource environments, where the speed and number of computers and internet access may be varied; 2) issues related to language and accessibility of the database for its users; 3) the complexity of spatial data and spatially-organized digital archives; 4) creative ways to make meaningful and useful links to the expansive corpus of

relevant materials; 5) user-driven storytelling, in contrast to prepared digital stories; 5) copyright and permissions issues from a range of institutions and countries; all while keeping in mind the 6) eventual expansion of the archive, its use and users, and its long-term sustainability. These challenges were seen as potential areas for collaboration with the AHRC/NEH project team and defined the subsequent efforts of the group, especially in relation to digital storytelling.

Survey of Digital Storytelling Initiatives across the Global South

As part of the background research associated with the grant, the project team evaluated other heritage digital archives and storytelling platforms across the Global South for similarities and differences, and for potential future directions for *metsemegologolo*. Given the broadness of the topics of digital storytelling and Global South, the team thought it was best to first search for and highlight those based on African and on African history and archaeology, and/or that engage with African museum objects. However, good comparatives were more limited than we initially hoped, especially at the extent and with the types of data that were of interest to our *metsemegologolo* collaborators, we broadened our considerations to include marginalized and/or difficult histories, such as those of the African American and other minorities' experiences in the United States. This proved especially productive for generating additional comparative content and, as described below, became the focus on the survey results. Comparative projects were categorized both based on the type of web resource (archive, exhibit, storytelling), the geographic region it involved, and whether the curated materials were archaeological, historical, or ethnographic in nature. Emphasis on websites that were engaging with digitized material beyond documents, especially with spatial and/or 3D data, helped sort through potential comparatives. There seemed a major gap – and a real need – for quality, educational resources about the African precolonial period, the emphasis of our partner project. Further, there appeared a need to engage with a wider set of materials beyond the written archive. Within African history, it is known that the comparative paucity of written documents, especially written by Africans from an African perspective, has skewed interpretations of historical encounters, reinforcing (even if indirectly and unintentionally) the viewpoints of white, male, colonial powers. Within African studies, this led to the development of placing oral histories on par with the written record (e.g., Vansina 1961). A similar foundational movement within historical archaeology (e.g., Ferguson 1977) and the humanities (e.g., Prown 1982) helped to posit material cultural analysis as a complementary, and at times contradictory, source of information providing insights about human behavior. Those movements have continued to mature and grow into the digital space.

The review highlights one project of high relevance, the Rising Above archive and visualization (<http://risingabove.cast.uark.edu>). Rising Above focuses on the history of Japanese-American internment in Arkansas during World War II. Importantly here, it is a fully-fledged project that involves the archaeological and historical records broadly across a wide set of materials, including spatial and visual components; that desire a relational database; and that promote a marginalized and difficult histories that become relatable to an interested public. Although the location lies outside of the Global South, the content and structure generated the greatest source for conversation among the group.

The survey results and the featured project, Rising Above, helped guide conversation at the NEH-AHRC workshop that was held in Cambridge in September 2022 and a rich source for inviting speakers for the NEH-AHRC webinar held in March 2023, both of which are elaborated upon below.

US-UK Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms Workshop, September 12-14, 2022

The Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms US-UK workshop was held in at the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research at the University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK from September 12-14, 2022. The workshop brought together 13 archaeological and geospatial experts from six different institutions to discuss how metsemegologolo might serve as a model for similar efforts, reviewing its successes and challenges to date and providing recommendations for future efforts.

The morning of the first day focused on an overview of the metsemegologolo project. Representatives from metsemegologolo outlined the near-term and long-term objectives from the project and the variety of educational themes the project was hoping to emphasize. Since over a year had passed since the NEH/AHRC collaboration was initially proposed, metsemegologolo updated the group on progress, such as digital curations and planned activities, as well as provided an internal assessment of current needs. These needs provided a base for engagement with the US workshop contributors, from the Center for Advanced Spatial Technologies (CAST) at the University of Arkansas, for potential avenues for collaboration. The first afternoon reviewed technological and cultural barriers that digital initiatives such as metsemegologolo face in South Africa, and in the Global South more widely. The group examined comparative digital projects that involved spatial archives and/or digital storytelling components that focused on archaeology and African history and the history of various marginalized communities in the United States. CAST representatives presented their experiences with building a relational database for a WWII Japanese-American internment camp, Rohwer, which was also the focus of the comparative projects review (<https://risingabove.cast.uark.edu>). The second day involved a review of the archival structure of the metsemegologolo database. Discussion was oriented around the process of digital archiving of archaeological and ethnographic objects, associated datasets, maps, written documents, and audio and visual recordings. The group discussed the types of spatial and nonspatial data the project involved and the digitization and visualization methods the project was using; reviewed the project standards for data collection, paradata, and metadata and the workflow pipelines; and, at a macro level, begin to think about the intended userbase, future scaling and efficiency efforts, and potential issues with storage, access, and sustainability. The final day focused on how metsemegologolo might be mobilized for digital storytelling. The group discussed best practices for storytelling, especially for doing so successfully in the Global South. Key to this debate was considering the use of ESRI StoryMaps versus an open-source platform such as Omeka; reflecting on colonial legacies in Africa and how best to encourage multiple narratives and interpretations; and integrating topical themes into the national (RSA) history curriculum. The afternoon was spent consolidating the summaries from the workshop, identifying next phases of collaborations, and preparing for a planned webinar on digital storytelling in March 2023.

“Digital Storytelling in the Global South” Webinar, March 14, 2023

As part of the *“Digital Storytelling on African Urbanism”* project, PIs Klehm and Merlo organized a virtual seminar on digital storytelling in low-resourced educational environments in the Global South. Hosted by the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research at the University of Cambridge, the webinar sought to benefit US and UK institutions, and scholars and institutions across the Global South who are also working to address digital-enabled equitable participation. Titled, “Digital Storytelling in the Global South: Utilizing Spatial Archives for Diverse Audiences,” the webinar explored how archaeologists, historians, museum experts, and educators can engage with emerging digital technologies to explore the past alongside the public. The webinar took place on March 14, 2023, over the course of three hours. The webinar was facilitated by the project PIs, Carla Klehm (US) and Stefania Merlo (UK).

“Digital Storytelling in the Global South” brought together experts in archaeology and beyond to discuss three themes:

1. Storytelling with spatial archives, on how various forms of spatial data can be incorporated into and structured within archival databases for digital storytelling;
2. Digital infrastructure in low-resourced environments, on the logistical challenges with connecting audiences with varying technical competencies, computer and internet speeds, and cultural understandings and language barriers to resources associated with digital publication;
3. Digital storytelling and the narrative voice, on how marginalized voices and perspectives can be integrated into digital storytelling process, empowering communities to engage with storytelling in self-directed, generative ways that deepen connections to cultural heritage.

Each theme is an hour in length, with time dedicated equally to presentation and audience participation. The webinar was recorded for open-access publication online, with the consent of the participants. The videos are divided into three sessions that follow the session presentations and discussions on each of the three topics (storytelling with spatial data, digital infrastructure in low-resource environments, and digital storytelling and the narrating voice). The webinar recordings are available on the metsemegologolo website, at <https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/digital-storytelling/neh-ahrc-digital-storytelling-webinar/>.

A primary objective of the webinar was to bring together a range of scholars from a variety of disciplines across the digital humanities. In our earlier survey of other digital storytelling and archival initiatives, we had recognized a siloing of examples and dialogues that paralleled traditional academic disciplines: archaeologists tended to talk to other archaeologists, historians to other historians, etc., even though important projects were emerging in geography, information sciences, and even engineering. Part of our recruitment effort, then, included:

- Featuring projects based in the Global South, as these tend to not have as widespread international attention (and funding support) as their Global North counterparts;

- Promoting leadership by underrepresented scholars;
- Fostering a multidisciplinary conversation, where fields of expertise range, and a variety of universities, museums, and non-profits could share their comparative efforts;
- Highlighting research on African and African American prehistory, history, and culture.

During the webinar, there were 167 participants. While some people logged in for specific sessions or presentations, only 12 users stayed for less than 40 minutes. Approximately half of the users were based in Africa. Overall, the project team was impressed by the strong interest among the digital humanities community that these topics and this format generated, especially for engaging with audiences in the Global South.

Digital Storytelling Project Website and Digital Curations

As both a place to gather resources and make available the results of this project, we built a landing page for the Digital Storytelling Project within the metsemegologolo website: <https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/digital-storytelling/>. Metsemegologolo already had a growing user base, in association with its other efforts (e.g., an ongoing Mellon project, multiple MSc and PhD theses that were based on it). As much of the AHRC/NEH project was in service of strengthening metsemegologolo, while placing it in wider dialogue with the digital humanities, the location seemed the most appropriate and, given the larger archive's trajectory, sustainability beyond this NEH/AHRC effort. Within the Digital Storytelling Project section, webpages provided additional information about the project, the project funders, the digital storytelling team, the metsemegologolo digital curations, digital storytelling resources, and recordings from the digital storytelling webinar.

As part of this project and other metsemegologolo initiatives, ESRI Story Maps and Omeka site were evaluated as multimedia platforms for the teaching of history and archaeology to secondary school and lower level university students in southern Africa. Previously created and newly crafted digital curations feature a variety of topics selected by the metsemegologolo group for its relevancy to South African history curriculum, high degree of interest among potential users, and the range and strength of digital collections involved. These themes included Moleta, the kind of the Bangwaketse peoples of southern Africa in the late 18th century; Seoke, the first capital city of the Bangwaketse; mobility among Tswana groups in the 18th and 19th century; and a virtual exploration of a 1h-19th century Iron Age site in South Africa. The digital curations are found at: <https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/research/storymaps/>.

Future Directions

One of the most unexpected but universally agreed upon recommendation from the initial workshop was that, in the Global South, museums provide the best loci for deploying digital storytelling with students. Variability in numbers and qualities of computer labs, internet access, and digital literacy make school-centric efforts challenging, especially for schools that service communities in poorer areas. In South Africa as in the United Kingdom and the United States, many public schools take trips at least once a year to nearby cultural and historical museums; there is an opportunity to use museums as an equaliser for access to technology. The opportunity for museum to utilise the materials that are not on display, especially when this comprises the

vast majority of collections, also provides an exciting avenue and rich corpus of materials to draw from. Further, museum resources can be used by hundreds of classrooms from dozens of schools, providing an opportunity for greater sustainability than one that requires dozens (and potentially hundreds) of school- and classroom-level interventions. However, with new directions come new directions. Museum-based storytelling needs to be a brief enough encounter and a short enough read to fit within a larger one-day museum visit, aligning with school curriculum standards with articulating with the strengths of a museum's collection. The project concluded that research focusing on how to quickly and effectively digital skills to curators and educators would help museum-based digital storytelling be deployable at local levels, including making those methods adaptable in a variety of museum settings.

With reference to the digital storytelling curations themselves, the group had a robust discussion on whether to continue to prepare curations ahead of time, or focus on self-directed curations where some or all of the story is generated by the user. We discussed relative strengths and the feasibility of each approach. With prepared curations, a guided tour through the archive would allow the user to access quality content with perhaps less apprehension of exploring new content and making the most meaningful use of the archive, at least with respect to utilizing a variety of sources and media types (provided that was a strength of the curation), or for exploring a particular topic that the user may not have otherwise considered or explored in the same way. Beyond a lower barrier to entry use, it also requires less technical skill from the user, as prepared curations do not require aggregating and linking content together. A prepared curation would also be less time-intensive, delivering content to the users in an active, engaging manner that complements other forms of teaching. However, predetermined curations are not necessarily flexible in terms of content and have a relatively fixed amount of time for exploration that might be too long or too short depending on the lesson and pedagogy goals. Content may cover material that is already known, less interesting, or targeted for a different grade level. Lastly, the top-down model has the potential to fall into a neocolonial trap wherein (scientific) knowledge is known and gate-kept by outside experts. The group also discussed the potential for prepared curations to at least be used as examples for self-generative curations. A middle-ground was suggested through the idea of prepared mini-curations that would link together a few concepts and items that users could either learn from (those connections, relationships between various data types) or even directly build from and incorporate within their own curations. The analogy from the group was to offer a couple puzzle pieces that were already linked together to build from. Mini-curations, or even encouraging self-generated mini-curations (as opposed to fuller, long-form curations) could allow for more short-term engagements by the user and/or for narrower lesson plans where relevant content might be far more limited in nature.

With museums as a locus and self-directed curations in mind, project PIs Merlo and Klehm applied for the AHRC Follow on Funding for US and Ireland Digital Humanities Collaboration, which is under consideration at the time of this report.